

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B300
Date: 25 June 2007
Take Off: 09:25:56
Landing: 14:18:44
Flight Time: 4h 52m 48s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Nouakchott -> Niamey

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Core chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	CCM2	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	Christian Gram	Leeds University
15	DFL ops	Keith Drummond	Directflight

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B300
 Date: 25 June 2007
 Project: GERBIL
 Location: Nouakchott -> Niamey

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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091136		GIN	-.03 kft	074	on
091153		inu	-.03 kft	074	to navigate
091211		cgps	-.03 kft	074	b300cgps.log
091225		bbr	-.03 kft	074	extend
091237		Heimann	-.03 kft	074	closed
091256		psap	-.03 kft	074	flow off
092123	092421	pirouette	-.03 kft	268	275M
092556		T/O	-.05 kft	037	Nouakchott
092556	094859	Profile 1	0.56 - 21.0 kft	034	
092659		psap	0.86 kft	035	flow on at T/O
092723		Heimann	1.00 kft	045	open after T/O
092815		Video	1.6 kft	080	#1 ffc, #2 ufc for pirouette
092840		Video	1.9 kft	095	#1 ffc, #2 dfc at T/O
093205		TWC	4.7 kft	095	power cycled
094859	105133	Run 1.1	21.0 kft	097	
095000		bbr	21.0 kft	097	retract
095047		JW	21.0 kft	097	zero
095710		isdn	21.0 kft	085	isp failure
100051		Video	21.0 kft	086	#1 ffc, #2 set to ufc (cirrus)
102000		Sonde 1	21.0 kft	087	
103605		Video	21.0 kft	089	#2 ufc reset to dfc
105038		Sonde 2	21.0 kft	089	
105134	111549	Profile 2	21.0 - 2.2 kft	088	
105428		Video	18.4 kft	090	#1, #2 end
105455		Video	18.0 kft	090	#3 ffc, #4 dfc; started
105515		bbr	17.7 kft	091	extend
105534		heimann	17.4 kft	091	cal 11
111550	112849	Run 2.1	2.2 kft	089	
111614		bbr	2.2 kft	091	retract
112934		heimann	2.2 kft	137	cal 14
113207	114545	Run 2.2	2.2 kft	256	
114641	120427	Profile 3	2.4 - 23.1 kft	093	
114700		bbr	2.9 kft	092	extend
115607		P3	15.0 kft	095	interrupt
115729		P3	15.0 kft	269	resumed
120558	130029	Run 3.1	23.1 - 23.0 kft	271	
120501		bbr	23.0 kft	255	retract
120925		Sonde 3	23.0 kft	092	
121100		psap	23.0 kft	089	filter change @ 12:08
122752		Video	23.0 kft	090	#3, #4 end
122824		Video	23.0 kft	090	#5 ffc, #6 dfc; started
124416		Sonde 4	23.0 kft	122	
130030	130310	Profile 4	23.0 - 25.0 kft	127	
130310	133830	Run 4.1	25.0 kft	128	
133830	134836	Profile 5	25.0 - 13.0 kft	128	
133850		bbr	24.9 kft	128	extend
133908		Heimann	24.7 kft	128	cal 14
134836	140337	Run 5.1	13.0 kft	127	
134859		bbr	13.0 kft	127	retract
140338	141612	Profile 6	13.0 - 2.4 kft	134	
140526		video	11.7 kft	121	#7 ffc, #8 dfc started
141025		bbr	6.8 kft	118	extend in profile
141844		Land	0.76 kft	093	Niamey
142032	142332	pirouette	0.76 - 0.75 kft	113	120M

B300 Track 25-JUN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

Gerbils: Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget Intercomparison of Longwave and Shortwave radiation.

Flight No: B300

Date: 25th June 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ and remote sensing measurements of Saharan dust and the associated effect on solar and terrestrial radiation.

Location:

Over land areas between Nouakchott (Mauritania) and Niamey (Niger).

Points:

Alpha : SUGGESTED point at 18°N, 7°W.

Weather:

High loadings of dust aerosols. Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

TERRA: MISR overpass at point alpha at 11:07Z

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/wet-nephelometer combination

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS/SHIMS

ARIES

Flight pattern:

1. If clear from cloud, perform a 'pirouette' manoeuvre taking ~3minutes for a 360 turn.
2. Take off from Nouakchott at 10:00Z.
3. Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/minute towards the east until FL210 (25mins, T=25mins).
4. Perform a SLR (science speed not necessary) at this altitude towards Niamey (60mins, T=85mins) along 18°N.
5. Launch sonde.
6. Perform a profile descent down to MPA to reach point alpha. MARK POINT ALPHA (20mins, T=105mins).
7. Perform a SLR at MPA (may be soft-ride) eastwards for 12.5 minutes duration (15mins, T=110mins).
8. Perform reciprocal turn followed by SLR at MPA to reach point alpha (15 mins, T=135mins).
9. Perform a reciprocal turn followed by a broken profile ascent (initially eastwards, then westwards) to reach point alpha at FL250 (25mins, T=160mins).
10. Launch sonde.
11. Perform a SLR at FL250 in an eastwards direction along 18N, launching sondes where required (30mins, T=190mins).
12. At 18°N, ~4°W, make turn in the direction of Niamey.
13. Perform SLR at FL250 (65mins, T=255mins).
14. Profile descent into Niamey (25mins, T=280mins).
15. Perform a pirouette manoeuvre if skies are cloud free.

GERBIL flight between Nouakchott, Mauritania & Niamey, Niger

Scientific objective: To characterise the physical and radiative properties of mineral dust and the effect on solar and terrestrial radiation. The intense observations were made in conjunction with a MISR overpass at 11:07Z.

Weather conditions: The atmosphere was dusty, but the very high levels of blowing dust that had been experienced on other flights was not found.

Flight pattern:

Again, another successful flight. The aircraft took off from Nouakchott around 09:25, and performed a profile to the east. Dust with an estimated aerosol optical depth of around 0.7 was encountered with a top at approximately FL170. The aerosol had a strange inverted profile with the highest scattering ($\sim 170 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$) at high altitude. A SLR was performed at FL210 to the east and a sonde was dropped halfway along this run. A sonde was dropped. A profile descent was then made to point alpha (18N, 7W). A SLR was performed at minimum permitted altitude to the east along the 18N line of latitude for approximately 13 minutes, a procedural turn was then made and a reciprocal run at MPA performed. The aerosol optical depth appeared to be around 0.7 (accounting for a 1.5 multiplication factor). The surface was very barren – yellow, red and white all in evidence and some larger blackish rocks. Filters were exposed during these runs. A reciprocal turn and a broken profile ascent was then made back to point alpha. A further sonde was dropped. A long SLR at FL250 was then made along 18N and another sonde dropped just after turning towards Niamey. A profile descent was made to FL130 followed by a SLR at this level where the scattering reached $50 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$. A filter was exposed on this leg. A profile descent was made to FL50, and then into Niamey.

Flight summary:

The area close to the MISR overpass was intensively characterised and provides a dust environment free from cloud. SWS/SHIMS and ARIES were used to measure the radiation and the

Instrument problems:

PCASP now appears to be working.

CO now working (leak detected and rectified on flight B299).

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B 300** Date 25th June 07 Name Jim Heywood Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					T = 24°C.
					Good conditions for pirouette.
~09:22 09:21:23					Start pirouette. End of runway. No cloud above. Good
					Quite dusty above. pirouette.
~09:25 09:24:21	P1↑				End pirouette. Vis ~ 5nm.
09:29					Red dunes & white strips of sand below. Dustier at 2500ft (visually).
09:48:59	$\frac{E \rightarrow P1}{S \rightarrow R17}$	$\overrightarrow{FL210}$	97	175°4' / 14° 2' W	A little Ci above at very high level,
09:55					Swap to recording down upward camera to detect Ci.
10:10					Still some Ci above. Just dust below.

Mission Scientist's Log

C U
 1 1 3 1 1 3 1 1
 D C U 1 D 1
 1 1 3 1

Flight No **B-300** Date **25/06/07** Name **Jim Haywood** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:15					Disapating Cb visible to far right > 200 miles away. Ci above seems to be associated with this.
10:20	R1.1	FL210 →			Launch sander #1 Ci above..
10:26					Ci clearing - should be free in ~10 mins.
10:35					Free from Ci. ^{Upper & lower BBRs useable from ~10:30.} Swap recording camera from upward to downward.
10:35	R1.1	FL210 →			Interference on BBRs (incl pyrometer) due to HF comms.
10:50:38					Launch sander #2.
10:51:33	End R1.1 St P2	FL210 ↓			Profile descent to α.
		FL25 FL200			Point α
11:15:50	End P2 St R2.1	FL20	92		Dusty above, no cloud surface Flat but variable red/white surface, some rocks

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B 300** Date **25/06/07** Name **Jim Haywood** Page **3** of **Bf**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Tephi shows surface close to 45C.
11:28:50	End R2.1	FL20 →			Procedural turn onto reciprocal
11:32:07	St R2.2	FL20 →			
11:45:45	End R2.2	FL20 →			Reciprocal turn
11:46:41	St P3	FL20 ↑	100	18, 6048'	
11:56:07	Int P3	FL150 →			V.V.V. Avin Ci to RHS
11:57:29	Restart P3	FL150 ↑			Not affecting ARIES or pyrometers.
12:04:27	End P3	FL230 →			End profile
					Reciprocal turn
12:04:27	St R3.1	FL230 →			Point X
		FL230 →			Launch sonda #3.
~12:18					At point β (end of low-level track) All looks very good. MISR, MODIS, O-7Y dust + aircraft all aligned.
~					Continue along 18°N.
12:42					Make turn towards Niuey Some Ci ahead ahead, not affecting any radar measurements
12:44:16					Launch sonda #4.
12:	End R3.1 St P4	FL230 ↑			Go higher to conserve fuel.
	End P4 St R4.1	FL250 →			Upper BBRs will be affected by Ci from 13:07.
13:08					Some scattered Cu below.

B300

Flight Manager

NOUAKHOTPT
09:25:56

- ✓ WOW
- ✓ EIN
- INU
- ✓ CEPS
- TW
- BBR/HEIMANN
- ✓ JW
- _____
- ✓ PSAP flow

ETA 14:30Z

- TW off
- BBR/HEIMANN
- PSAP flow
- ✓ CEPS
- ✓ INU
- ✓ EIN
- ✓ WOW

LAND
NIAMEY
14:18:44

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 300

Date: 25/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:08:00	DAU1 Time: +1	DAU2 Time: +1	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:25:56																Start P1 from takeoff	
09:29:00	210	0.09	1	15	3											FL020	
09:30:08	205	0.10		20	3											FL030	
09:31:15	190	0.10		20	3											FL040	
09:32:27	195	0.10		40	3											FL050	
09:33:36	160	0.10	2	40	3											FL060	
09:34:50	120	0.10		40	3											FL070	
09:35:47	100	0.12		50	5											FL080	
09:36:51	100	0.12		60	5											FL090	
09:37:39	85	0.13		60	6											FL100	
09:38:41	100	0.14		60	3											FL110	
09:39:37	90	0.13		50	1											FL120 PCASP heater on	
09:40:45	90	0.16	3	50	1											FL130	
09:41:37	110	0.15		60	5											FL140	
09:42:42	100	0.14		60	3											FL150	
09:43:38	100	0.17	4	50	3											FL160	
09:44:43	25	0.20		5												FL170	
09:45:55	10	0.09		3												FL180	
09:46:50	5	0.09		2												FL190	
09:47:53	3	0.07		2												FL200	
09:48:56	3	0.06		1												End of P1 & Start Run 1.1 @ FL210	
09:50:00	3	0.06		1													
09:55:00	3	0.06		1													
10:00:00	3	0.06		1													
10:05:00	2	0.06		1													
10:10:00	3	0.06		1													
10:15:00	1	0.09		1													
10:20:00	1	0.10		1													
10:25:00	2	0.17		2													
10:30:00	2	0.04		1													
10:35:00	2	0.06		1													
10:40:00	1	0.07	5	1													
10:45:00	1	0.10		1													
10:50:00	1	0.12		1													
10:51:30																End of Run 1.1 & Start P2 from FL210	
10:52:40	2	0.17		1												FL200	
10:53:42	2	0.06		1												FL190	
10:54:49	5	0.07		1	1											FL180	
10:55:57	10	0.16		5	1											FL170	
10:56:58	60	0.12		30	3											FL160	
10:57:56	90	0.12	6	40	5											FL150	
10:59:05	90	0.13		40	5											FL140	
11:00:26	80	0.11		40	1											FL130	
11:02:05	100	0.11	7	50	8											FL120	
11:03:50	100	0.11		50	8											FL110	
11:05:34	110	0.12		50	8											FL100	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 300

Date: 25/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:08:00	DAU1 Time: +1	DAU2 Time: +1	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:06:56	125	0.12	8	60	3											FL090 PCASP heaters off	
11:08:16	150	0.12		70	6											FL080	
11:10:00	160	0.12	9	70	7											FL070	
11:11:26	150	0.12	10	70	7											FL060	
11:12:36	180	0.12	11	80	9											FL050	
11:13:44	160	0.11		70	10											FL040	
11:14:51	165	0.11	12	60	8											FL030	
11:15:51																End of P2 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL022	
11:16:00	190	0.12	13	60	8												
11:18:00	160	0.13	15	60	9												
11:20:00	190	0.13	17	60	8												
11:22:00	205	0.12	18	70	10												
11:24:00	200	0.12	19	80	10												
11:26:00	225	0.12	20	90	8												
11:28:45																End of Run 2.1	
11:32:05																Start Run 2.2 @ FL022	
11:33:00	225	0.13	25	90	8												
11:35:00	220	0.12		90	8												
11:37:00	200	0.13		90	9												
11:39:00	200	0.12		80	8												
11:41:00	190	0.12		70	7												
11:43:00	200	0.12		70	3												
11:45:00	160	0.12		70	3												
11:45:44																End of Run 2.2	
11:46:44																Start P3 from FL022	
11:47:08	150	0.11		60	4											FL030	
11:48:02	150	0.13		70	4											FL040	
11:48:46	150	0.13		70	2											FL050	
11:49:22	160	0.12		60	2											FL060	
11:50:07	155	0.13		60	4											FL070	
11:50:47	150	0.12		50	5											FL080	
11:51:40	125	0.11		50	6											FL090	
11:52:17	100	0.11		50	3											FL100	
11:53:01	105	0.11	26	50	2											FL110	
11:53:46	90	0.13	27	50	2											FL120 PCASP heater on	
11:54:35	90	0.14		20	2											FL130	
11:55:18	75	0.13		20	2											FL140	
11:56:05	80	0.13	28	20	3											FL150	
11:58:17	80	0.10		15	3											FL160	
11:58:58	40	0.08		3	3											FL170	
11:59:47	7	0.08		2	1											FL180	
12:00:38	9	0.08		1	1											FL190	
12:01:46	6	0.07		1												FL200	
12:02:46	6	0.07		1												FL210	
12:03:48	4	0.07		2												FL220	
12:04:30																End of P3 @ FL230	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 300

Date: 25/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:08:00	DAU1 Time: +1	DAU2 Time: +1	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:06:44																Start Run 3.1 @ FL230	
12:07:00	5	0.07	28														
12:09:00	7	0.08															
12:11:00	6	0.08															
12:13:00	5	0.08															
12:15:00	7	0.06															
12:17:00	5	0.07															
12:19:00	5	0.07	29		1												
12:21:00	2	0.07		1	1												
12:23:00	1	0.07		1	1												
12:25:00	1	0.11		1	1												
12:30:00	3	0.06		1													
12:35:00	3	0.05		1	1												
12:40:00	1	0.05			1												
12:45:00	2	0.07		1	1												
12:50:00	3	0.08															
12:55:00	1	0.07		1	1												
13:00:28																End of Run 3.1 & Start P4 from FL230	
13:01:48	2	0.07	30	1												FL240	
13:03:08																End of P4 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL250	
13:05:00	1	0.06		1													
13:10:00	3	0.07		1	1												
13:15:00	1	0.03															
13:20:00	1	0.06															
13:25:00	1	0.06		1													
13:30:00	1	0.05		1													
13:35:00	1	0.05		1													
13:38:28																End of Run 4.1 & Start P5	
13:39:47	1	0.05		1												FL240	
13:40:46	3	0.08		1												FL230	
13:39:31	4	0.07		1												FL220	
13:42:18	3	0.05		1												FL210	
13:43:01	3	0.08		1												FL200	
13:43:47	3	0.06		1												FL190	
13:44:34	4	0.06		1												FL180	
13:45:22	7	0.13		3												FL170	
13:46:10	15	0.14		10												FL160	
13:46:55	25	0.09		10												FL150	
13:47:44	60	0.12		20												FL140	
13:48:34																End of P5 & Start Run 5.1 @ FL130	
13:49:00	75	0.10	31	20	3												
13:51:00	75	0.10	32	30	5												
13:53:00	75	0.10		40	4												
13:55:00	75	0.11	33	30	3												
13:57:00	70	0.12		30	3												
13:59:00	70	0.12	34	30	4												

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B300

Date:

25 JUN 2007

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1_a	251-07	----	----	Bottom	11:15:50	11:28:49	R2.1	515	R2.1 .2.2 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~140 Mm-1, point alpha 18°N 16.9°W
Filters run1_a	252-07	----	----	Top	11:15:50	11:28:49	R2.1	716	
Filters run1_b	251-07	----	----	Bottom	11:32:07	11:45:45	R2.2	554	R2.2 2.2 kfeet 18°N 6°W, sigma_scatt ~170 Mm-1, sigma_scatt ~130 Mm-1 @11h43
Filters run1_b	252-07	----	----	Top	11:32:07	11:45:45	R2.2	759	
Filters run2	253-07	----	----	Bottom	12:00:00	13:35:00		---	BLANKS
Filters run2	254-07	----	----	Top	12:00:00	13:35:00		---	
Filters run3	255-07	----	----	Bottom	13:48:36	14:03:37	R5.1	184	R5.1 .1 FL050 in dust layer, sigma_scatt ~40 Mm-1
Filters run3	256-07	----	----	Top	13:48:36	14:03:37	R5.1	425	

B300_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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09:12:13.05 --- - - - -
09:12:13.05 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:12:13.05 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:12:13.05 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B300
09:12:13.05 --- - - - -
09:12:24.64 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:12:26.62 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:12:29.67 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:14:00.95 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
09:14:03.31 SWS - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
09:14:06.77 USH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
09:14:09.26 USH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
09:14:12.51 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:14:16.70 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:14:19.52 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:19.52 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:19.52 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:24.34 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
09:14:27.65 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:14:31.53 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
09:14:50.77 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:51.00 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:51.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:14:54.31 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:14:55.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:55.44 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:14:57.92 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:14:59.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:01.68 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:15:04.93 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:15:06.10 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:09.14 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:15:12.87 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:13.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:18.65 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
09:15:24.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:15:24.86 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:15:25.44 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:15:29.28 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:29.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:33.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:15:48.73 --- - - - - *** preflight OK
09:16:14.39 --- - - - - *** B300 flight Gerbils..Nouakchott to Niamey
09:16:47.40 --- - - - - *** SWS to 90Aft for taxi and take off
09:21:38.50 --- - - - - *** on ground pirouette manouvre
09:21:52.53 --- - - - - *** starting heading 275 coming left
09:22:10.60 --- - - - - *** SWS to 0 degrees for manouvre
09:24:22.21 --- - - - - *** end manouvre
09:24:34.66 --- - - - - *** sws to 90 AFT
09:25:39.70 --- - - - - *** take off and start P1
09:26:10.90 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
09:27:40.36 --- - - - - *** sws to 172 Aft for profile climb
09:28:01.54 --- - - - - *** aircrsft pitch 8 degrees
09:28:52.65 USH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
09:29:04.46 SWS - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
09:29:07.50 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:29:07.60 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:29:07.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:29:11.04 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:29:13.17 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:29:15.86 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:29:20.80 --- - - - - *** shutter sw inop
09:29:23.27 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:29:26.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:29:30.79 --- - - - - *** resetting
09:29:33.18 --- - - - - Reset shutters.

```

09:29:39.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:29:41.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:29:43.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:29:44.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:47.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:48.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:29:59.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** shutters ok now
09:33:37.87	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
09:33:39.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:33:45.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:36:40.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL090
09:48:57.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P1 at FL210 and Start R1.1
09:49:06.38	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
09:49:19.56	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
09:49:26.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:26.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:26.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:49:29.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:31.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:49:34.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:08.49	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
09:53:12.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:20.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:27.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 175 Aft
10:10:46.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** aircraft pitch 4.8 degrees
10:21:11.18	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
10:21:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:21:16.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:04.63	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:28:08.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:13.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:51:41.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r1.1 start P2
10:52:13.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 177 Aft for descent
10:52:22.39	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
10:52:24.99	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
10:52:28.65	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
10:52:33.41	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
10:52:36.21	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:52:37.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:38.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:38.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:52:40.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:42.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:46.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:24.71	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:54:46.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 4F for descent
10:54:53.40	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
10:54:56.79	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
10:55:00.00	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
10:55:04.14	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:55:19.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:27.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:04.30	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
10:59:07.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:14.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:14.26	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:02:16.88	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
11:02:18.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:02:23.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:03.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** in dust at FL110
11:07:19.75	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
11:07:22.76	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
11:07:25.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:29.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:15.11	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
11:10:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:10:19.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:24.57	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
11:15:28.28	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.

11:15:30.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:31.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:56.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile 2 start run 2.1
11:16:28.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:16:29.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:16:29.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:16:30.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:33.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:37.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:59.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 2500ft heading 090degrees
11:21:33.19	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:21:39.14	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
11:21:44.03	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
11:21:45.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:47.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:33.74	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:22:37.92	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
11:22:40.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:42.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:36.47	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
11:26:38.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:39.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:39.82	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:27:47.12	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 50ms.
11:27:50.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:52.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:03.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** end or run 2.1
11:29:28.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** next up a scanning run from 50 Aft to 50 fore
11:29:43.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** in 10 degree increments
11:31:08.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 50A in preparation
11:31:12.68	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
11:31:16.98	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
11:31:42.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50Aft
11:31:44.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:44.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:44.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:47.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:49.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:53.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:31:56.31	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:31:59.28	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
11:32:01.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:05.18	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:32:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:07.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:10.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:12.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** start scanning
11:33:15.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50 Fore
11:34:12.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40 AFT
11:35:11.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40 Fore
11:36:15.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30 AFT
11:36:23.89	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
11:36:26.92	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
11:36:29.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:31.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:16.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30 FORE
11:38:17.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 20 AFT
11:38:24.68	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
11:38:29.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:31.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:13.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 20 FORE
11:39:36.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 AFT
11:40:10.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 Aft now
11:40:17.05	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
11:40:19.60	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
11:40:22.33	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 25ms.
11:40:24.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:25.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

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11:41:11.22 --- - - - - *** 10 FORE
11:42:11.81 --- - - - - *** 0 degrees aircraft pitch 5.5 degrees
11:43:28.66 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
11:45:53.12 --- - - - - *** end run 2.2
11:46:47.16 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
11:46:54.67 --- - - - - *** start profile 3
11:47:00.36 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
11:47:03.90 SWS - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 300ms.
11:47:07.63 SWS - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
11:47:13.38 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:13.63 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:13.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:15.83 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:17.27 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:19.08 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:47.91 --- - - - - *** SWS to 171AFT for climb
11:55:58.56 --- - - - - *** sws to 172 Aft
11:56:11.57 --- - - - - *** interrupt profile at FL150
11:57:37.52 --- - - - - *** resume P3
11:58:10.88 --- - - - - *** nearing top of dust
11:58:57.12 --- - - - - *** at FL160
12:03:20.46 --- - - - - *** end P2 at FL240
12:03:25.04 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
12:03:28.11 LSH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
12:03:32.72 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
12:04:28.74 --- - - - - *** end P3 at FL230
12:04:34.10 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
12:05:49.94 --- - - - - *** turning
12:06:44.13 --- - - - - *** start r3.1
12:06:49.51 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
12:06:55.02 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:06:55.09 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:06:55.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:06:57.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:06:58.86 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:07:02.95 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:13:03.41 --- - - - - *** SWS to 175 AFT
12:13:09.38 LSH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
12:13:12.24 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:13:20.18 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:26:32.56 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:26:32.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:26:32.77 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:26:35.21 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:26:36.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:26:41.67 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:00:56.47 --- - - - - *** end r3.1 start P4
13:03:14.59 --- - - - - *** end P4 start R4.1
13:03:26.77 --- - - - - *** at FL250
13:21:24.43 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:21:24.76 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:21:24.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:21:27.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:21:27.91 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:21:32.90 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:38:46.91 --- - - - - *** end R4.1 start Profile descent 5
13:48:41.62 --- - - - - *** end P5 start r5.1
13:48:51.42 --- - - - - *** at FL130
13:54:01.13 --- - - - - *** scattered cumulus below and cirrus above
13:54:44.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:54:45.43 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:54:45.91 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:54:48.96 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:54:50.19 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:54:53.38 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:03:57.82 --- - - - - *** end run start P6
14:11:48.13 --- - - - - *** on approach to Niamey.
14:12:06.98 --- - - - - *** SWS to 90 AFT for landing.
14:16:53.12 --- - - - - *** end profile

```

14:20:33.72	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
14:20:36.43	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
14:20:41.56	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
14:21:02.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** on ground pirouette start
14:21:09.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 0 Deg
14:21:13.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:21.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:44.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** pirouette start heading 120 turning left
14:23:35.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** end pirouette
14:23:40.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** data stop

ARIES flight log

Flight: B300

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Date: 25/JUN/07 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NOUAKCHOTT TO NIAMEY

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 42 25	on the pen.	1x60	CH	C	—	—	D'oh! Scanner not switched on!
08 49	-	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Ah! That's better!
09 25	TAKE OFF						CH = Script (1x60 CBS, 1x60 HPS)
09 48 22	FL210	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
09 49 42	R111 "	480x1	N	C	71	41	Dusty below, but surface is visible. Crabbe
09 53 52		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
09 55 06		480x1	N	C	71	41	Banking at first
09 59 07		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 00 24		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 04 27		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 05 54		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 09 55		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 11 13		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 15 16		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 16 38		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 20 41		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 21 56		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 25 58		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 27 28		360x1	N	C	71	41	
10 30 31		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 31 47		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 35 51		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 37 05		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 41 07		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 42 26		480x1	N	C	71	41	
10 47 15		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 48 23		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 49 40		120x1	Z	O	70	40	Just for variation, let's look up for a bit.
10 50 53		360x1	N	C	71	41	Aborted at end of run.
10 51 41	↓	1x60	CH	C	71	41	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B300

page 2 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]" ~~view~~: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 15 58	2500 ft ASL	1x60	CH	C			
11 17 05		480x1	Z	O	70	41	
11 21		120x1	N	C			
11 22		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
11 23 37		480x1	Z	O	70	42	
11 27 48		120x1	N	C			
11 28 52		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
11 31 45		1x60	CH	C	71	43	CBB drifting up - this seems to happen a lot at low level in the tropics.
11 33 03		480x1	Z	O	70	43	
11 37 11		120x1	N	C	71	44	
11 38 16		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
11 39 27		480x1	Z	O	71	45	
11 43 34		120x1	N	C	71	46	
11 44 38		1x60	CH	C	71	46	
11 06 40	FL250	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 07 53		480x1	N	C	71	41	Dusty below, but surface still visible. some vegetation
11 11 59		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 13 14		480x1	N	C	71	41	
11 17 17		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 19 14		360x1	N	C	71	41	
12 22 15		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 23 43		480x1	N	C	71	42	
12 27 47		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 29		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 33 01		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 34 15		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 38 21		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 39 35		480x1	N	C	71	41	Dusty, but surface still visible. no vegetation
12 43 39		1x60	CH	C	70	41	
12 44 59		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 48 55		1x60	CH	C	71	41	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B300

page 3 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12 50 10	FL230	480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 54 13	..	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 56 04		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 00 06	↑	1x60	CH	C	71	42	
13 03	FL250	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 04 30	..	480x1	N	C	71	41	
13 08 32		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 09 50		480x1	N	C	71	41	
13 13 51		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 15 08		480x1	N	C	71	41	
13 19 10		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 20 25		480x1	N	C	71	41	Small patchy Cu below, Ci above.
13 24 27		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 25 59		360x1	Z	O	70	41	Let's look at the Ci for a while.
13 29 55		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 31 17		360x1	Z	O	70	41	
13 35 44		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 37 01		360x1	Z	O	70	41	Aborted at end of run.
13 39 37		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 48 38	FL130	1x60	CH	C			
13 49 51		240x1	Z	O	70	41	Ci above, some dust.
13 51 59		240x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, some Cu, some negative
13 54 01		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 55 25		240x1	Z	O	71	41	Aborted near start as acquisition seemed not to be occurring.
13 56 15		240x1	Z	O	70	41	
13 58 19		240x1	N	C	71	41	
14 00 22		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
14 01 48		240x1	Z	O	70	40	Aborted near end due to end of run.
14 04 54		1x60	CH	C	71	41	

Flight:

B300

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezovorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:49:46

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

26/06/2007 11:50:23

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B300

Date: 25 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

AOD T+24 (plotted 18z24/06/07)

At 12Z on 25/ 6/2007, from 12Z on 24/ 6/2007

0.05

0.1

0.2

0.4

0.8

1.6

3.2

6.4

12.8

total cloud cover [%]

total cloud cover [%]

total cloud cover [%]

GrADS: COLA/IGES

2007-06-24-20:26

Sunday 24 June 2007 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Monday 25 June 2007 12UTC

Low, L+M, Medium, M+H, High, H+L, H+M+L clouds

Cloud Cover T+36 (plotted 07z24/06/07)

At 12Z on 25/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 24/ 6/2007

6hr Precip Accum T+30 to 36

Surface Dust concentration T+36 (plotted 07z24/06/07)

At 12Z on 25/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 24/ 6/2007

2000-5000ft Dust concentration T+36

Dust conc 20.000o merid xsect

At 12Z on 25/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 24/ 6/2007

At 12Z on 25/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 24/ 6/2007

B300 Images Emailed In Flight

EEA041 MSG dust RGB 25 Jun 2007 0700 UTC

EEA041.jpg

MET9 25 JUN 2007 0600 BNW IR_108 5

SDDI-20070625-0600-BNW-09-IR_108-05-600.jpg

MET9 25 JUN 2007 0900 BNW IR_108 5

SDDI-20070625-0900-BNW-09-IR_108-05-600.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 25 Jun 2007 0800 UTC

0706250800_EAA051.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 25 Jun 2007 0800 UTC

0706250800_EEA041.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 25 Jun 2007 1000 UTC

0706251000_EAA051.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 25 Jun 2007 1000 UTC

0706251000_EEA041.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 25 Jun 2007 1200 UTC

0706251200_EAA051.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 25 Jun 2007 1200 UTC

0706251200_EEA041.jpg

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B300:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
4 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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